

Supplementary Material for the Paper “Facial Analysis Systems and Down Syndrome”

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A Rules of reference of the services

The following instructions are suggestions found in the documentation of the models in order to perform well and correctly.

A.1 AWS Rekognition

1. Age prediction: *”Amazon Rekognition estimates the lower and upper age for the person. In this case, the wider the age range, the lower the confidence for that prediction. As an approximation, you should use the mid-point of the age range to estimate a single value for the age of the detected face.*
2. Confidence Value: *We recommend using a threshold of 99 or more for use cases where the accuracy of classification could have any negative impact on the subjects of the images.*
3. Gender classification: *Amazon Rekognition makes gender binary (man, woman, girl, etc.) predictions based on the physical appearance of a person in a particular image. This kind of prediction is not designed to categorize a person’s gender identity, and you shouldn’t use Amazon Rekognition to make such a determination. For example, a Male actor wearing a long-haired wig and earrings for a role might be predicted as Female.*
4. Data Retention: Talking about the DetectFace and DetectLables models: *These are referred to as non-storage API operations because when you make the operation call, Amazon Rekognition does not persist any information discovered about the input image. Like all other Amazon Rekognition API operations, no input image bytes are persisted by non-storage API operations.*

A.2 ClarifAI

1. Cropped images: In the guideline of gender/age demographics recognition models, it is specified that *This model requires cropped face images to work properly.*
2. Data retention: *We retain Personal Data about you for as long as you have an open account with us or as otherwise necessary to provide Services to you or the Service User that provided us with your Personal Data. In some cases we retain Personal Data for longer, for example if we retain your Personal*

Data to train our models and models, to improve our Services, or if doing so is necessary to comply with our legal obligations, resolve disputes or collect fees owed, and as otherwise permitted or required by applicable law, rule or regulation, or if you or the Service User that provided us with your Personal Data have given us express consent to retain Personal Data for longer. We may also further retain information in an anonymous or aggregated form where that information would not identify you personally.

B Additional Tables and Figures

Table 1: Names of the specific models used for each prediction task.

	Gender	Age	Concept
AWS Rekognition	detect faces	detect faces	detect labels
ClarifAI	gender-demographics -recognition	age-demographics -recognition	general-image -recognition

Table 2: Labels of gender and age prediction models.

	Gender	Age
AWS Rekognition	Male/Female	random ranges
ClarifAI	Masculine/Feminine	[0-2, 3-9, 10-19, 20-29, 30-39, 40-49, 50-59, 60-69, 70-100]